

References

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Action of Dinitrogen tetroxide and its Thermal Dissociation Products on Anhydrous Neutral Alkali Salts of Tetrachlorophthallic Acid

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THE present work is in continuation of the work done by one of the authors (V.T.O.)¹ and is now extended to study the action of dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on neutral anhydrous sodium, potassium and lithium tetrachlorophthalate. It is interesting to observe that lithium salt behaves in slightly different manner than the sodium and potassium salts; especially in its behaviour with nitrogen dioxide above room temperature

The reaction of nitrogen gases on neutral sodium salts of some organic monobasic and dibasic acids have been investigated in past by Rodinov and Oblisteva² and reviewed by Riebsomer and Reineke³. Further work was published by one of the authors (V T O)¹

Experimental

Neutral salts of the tetrachlorophth acid were prepared by the method suggested in the literature⁴. Their purity was established by determining the weight of sulphates formed by the treatment with conc H_2SO_4 . The preparation of dinitrogen tetroxide and the experimental technique were the same as described by Oza⁵. The residue was first extracted with suitable organic solvent to remove organic compounds formed. It was later treated with water to dissolve inorganic compounds formed. Nonaqueous extracts after evaporating to dryness were analysed by standard methods. It showed presence of the anhydride. The qualitative analysis of the water extract showed the presence of nitrate ions together with the unreacted salt. The quantitative determination of nitrate was done by standard method⁶.

Results and Discussion

Results of the experiments indicate that sodium and potassium salts react completely with dinitrogen tetroxide and the reaction may be formulated as under. The lithium salt, however, behaves in a slightly different manner. The ionic species⁷ present

TABLE—TETRACHLOROPHTHALATE—LIQUID DINITROGEN TETROXIDE SYSTEM

Expt. No.	Substance taken	Liquid N_2O_4 taken	Nitrate formed	Anhydride formed	N_2O_4 used up	N_2O_3 formed
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
(a) System Na-Chlorophthalat + Liquid N_2O_4						
1.	0.0502 (1.40)	0.2445 (26.6)	0.02455 (2.88)	0.0413 (1.44)	0.0272 (3.00)	0.01095 (1.44)
2.	0.0750 (2.15)	0.2875 (31.20)	0.0368 (4.30)	0.0615 (2.15)	0.0397 (4.30)	0.0165 (2.17)
(b) System K-Chlorophthalat + Liquid N_2O_4						
3.	0.0500 (1.31)	0.2155 (23.24)	0.0266 (2.60)	0.0375 (1.31)	0.0242 (2.60)	0.0100 (1.32)
4.	0.0825 (2.17)	0.2754 (29.90)	0.0440 (4.30)	0.0623 (2.18)	0.0400 (4.30)	0.0165 (2.18)
(c) System Li-Chlorophthalate + Liquid N_2O_4						
5.	0.0500 (1.60)	0.2155 (23.4)	0.0161 (2.3)	0.0334 (1.17)	0.0216 (2.30)	0.0089 (1.17)
6.	0.0701 (2.20)	0.2369 (25.8)	0.0212 (3.00)	0.0438 (1.53)	0.0284 (3.10)	0.0117 (1.54)
7.	0.0510 (1.62)	0.2059 (22.4)	0.0218 (3.15)	0.0454 (1.61)	0.0292 (3.20)	0.0120 (1.58)
8.	0.072 (2.28)	0.2100 (22.8)	0.0285 (4.10)	0.0592 (2.08)	0.0385 (4.20)	0.0158 (2.08)

Figures in () indicate gram molecules (multiplied by 10^{-4})

Expts No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, were conducted at 0°C

Expts No. 1 to 4 were conducted for 1/2 hr. and 100% reaction took place.

Expts No. 5 and 6 were conducted for 24 hrs.

Expts No. 7 and 8 were conducted for 1 hr.

in the liquid dinitrogen tetroxide seem to be responsible for this reaction.

The results of experiments conducted at higher temperatures, (Fig. 1). indicate that the lithium salt does not react with nitrogen dioxide and its thermal dissociation products between 50° to 250°

Fig. 1.

when the period of contact was half an hour. The reaction which otherwise proceeds quantitatively like the sodium and potassium salts may be formulated as under :

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Alkyl anilines as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in Nitric Acid

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PRIMARY aromatic amines have previously been investigated¹ as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in HNO₃. The present paper describes the performance of Nimethyl aniline, N,N',dimethyl aniline, N,ethyl aniline, N,N',diethyl aniline as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in nitric acid.

Experimental

Cold rolled 63/37 brass, quarter hard temper, supplied by "Kamani metals and alloys limited", was used for experimental study. The preparation